

Sustainability and smartphone

- Working conditions, rare earths and precious metals, design

How do I make my website more sustainable?

1. Fewer images or lower resolution

2. Videos not on autoplay

3. As little advertising, tracking & cookies as possible

4. Where possible, avoidance of dynamic content (photo carousel etc.)

5. Use system fonts

How can I design an app more sustainably?

1. Hosting the server with providers that use 100% renewable energy

2. Reduce resolution of videos, images & avoid AI-generated content

3. Include as few app messages as possible

4. Use night mode where possible - this requires less energy

5. Optimize the app for as few clicks as possible